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UNPATH'D WATERS: Transforming the English Marine Heritage Record

Research Report: Work Package 6

Hefin Meara, Raghdaa Eissa and
Frankie Lau

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	2
1.1 Design of Mariner Data Models	2
1.2 Utilising GIS technologies to showcase HE marine data through web mapping applications	3
1.3 Enhancing the NMHR – approaches to recording a spatial depiction for shipwrecks whose precise location is unknown	13
1.4 Conclusions and final thoughts	23
Bibliography.....	24

1. Introduction

Historic England's National Marine Heritage Record is an extensive text-based dataset on the marine historic environment. The Unpath'd Waters project provided an opportunity to explore alternative forms of dissemination of this data, with a focus on story-telling and the use of visual aids to provide interesting and interactive ways to engage with what can otherwise be perceived as dry and unengaging data. This has the dual benefit of providing an eye-catching way to draw the attention of non-specialist users, but also an opportunity to detect patterns in the data that would otherwise be hidden away.

During the course of the Unpath'd Waters project Historic England has been working on the redevelopment of its National Marine Heritage Record using an instance of the Getty Conservation Institute's Arches open-source cultural heritage inventory platform. Arches¹ is a graph-based database, with information held in a semantically rich manner. The Historic England team have created bespoke data models suitable for holding information on the marine historic environment. The design of these models has been an iterative process, and the Unpath'd Waters GIS and visualisation strand of work has served as a testing ground for what information should be held in structured fields and controlled vocabularies. This will ease the automation and creation of specific visualisation methods for sharing data.

1.1 Design of Mariner Data Models

The development of the storymaps and web visualisations based around voyages and wartime incidents has highlighted the need for additional indexing fields, to allow for straightforward exporting of data from the National Marine Heritage Record (NMHR), for direct ingest into the visualisation software. Data models have been expanded to allow for the recording of voyages other than the final voyage. This is useful for recording notable voyages, such as Charles Darwin's voyages on board the Beagle, which ended its life as Coast Guard Watch Vessel No. 7, and lies buried in a mud berth on the River Roach on the Essex coastline².

Such additional indexing fields also address the split of shipwreck related information into two distinct models, one for the shipwreck site on the seabed, and one for the vessel from which the wreck is derived. Recording the information for the vessel as a separate and distinct entity, allows for the enhancement of records with information relating to floating vessels. This is particularly helpful for building linkages between national bodies such as Historic England, who have curatorial responsibility for wrecks on the seabed, and with National Historic Ships UK, which advises on matters relating to historic vessels in the UK, and curates data relating to the National Historic Fleet. Previously it has been difficult to compare the significance of floating vessels with their submerged counterparts. Improvements to the data structure delivered through the development of Mariner allow for improved comparisons between the two types of heritage assets. This is demonstrated by the timeline showing the various voyages undertaken by HMS Warrior³ created as part of the Unpath'd Waters project.

The development of stories and visualisations relating to the First World War has highlighted the need for improved linkages between shipwrecks and the vessels responsible for their sinking. The previous data

¹ <https://www.archesproject.org/>

² <https://historicengland.org.uk/listing/the-list/list-entry/1467785?section=official-list-entry>

³ <https://www.nationalhistoricalships.org.uk/register/501/hms-warrior>

structure allowed for the capture of general associations between wrecks, but these lacked any meaningful relationship. The new data structure specifically allows for the capture of associations such as “sunk by” and “sailed in convoy with”. Enhancing the data structure in this way allows for more detailed relationships to be recorded, and enables detailed visual representation to be built using the minimum of data enhancement prior to ingest into the visualisation software. This enhanced data structure has allowed for the accurate spatial depiction of German U-boat losses and their victims, allowing for previously unexplored patterns to be established (see below).

The development of the story maps and visualisations has identified key fields which need to be incorporated into the Mariner data export products, to allow ingest into the visualisation software without requiring an additional data cleansing stage of work. This will be incorporated into the Mariner system as the Historic England team develop custom reporting and data export tools.

1.2 Utilising GIS technologies to showcase HE marine data through web mapping applications

Unpath'd Waters offered Historic England's GIS Team the opportunity to test some novel approaches to visualising, using maps, charts, plots, and animations. These visual displays of information communicate data relationships and data-driven insights in an engaging and easily understandable manner. Data collections included NMHR records, marine geophysical survey data, and data outputs of specific projects (eg the Heritage Harbour Inventory project (Cattermole, A. 2023)). Data visualisation products were produced to showcase this varied data, including storymaps and web visualisations. Development of specialised applications or widgets allowed for visualisation of the data. A map-slider enabled the overlying of contemporary mapping with historic mapping and sea charts. Bathymetric data was used to create simple models of shipwreck sites, and fly-through animations were recorded to illustrate these models.

Web mapping applications are built using ESRI technologies, a leading GIS platform. ArcGIS Online (AGOL)⁴ is used to build the web apps, including Dashboards⁵, StoryMaps (SM)⁶, Experience Builder (ExB)⁷ in addition to Map Viewer and Scene Viewer⁸. Additionally, ArcGIS Pro⁹ is employed for data preparation, processing, and analysis before sharing to AGOL.

⁴ AGOL: A cloud-based GIS that enables organisations to collaborate and manage their data.

⁵ Dashboards: An online app within AGOL where web maps, lists, charts, gauges and indicators are integrated together in one screen

⁶ StoryMaps: ‘a story authoring web-based application that allows you to share your maps in the context of narrative text and other multimedia content.’ ESRI Documentation

⁷ ExB: An online app that allows the user to build web mapping apps that displays 2D and 3D data

⁸ Map Viewer and Scene Viewer: web mapping tools that allows the user to create, style and share 2D and 3D maps respectively.

⁹ ArcGIS Pro: a full-featured professional desktop GIS application

Figure 1: Workflow for producing the web apps. Most of the data is exported in formats that can be imported in ArcGIS Pro. Articles and other resources are used to add to the database and further understand the data at hand.

The data goes through a phase of revision, editing and preparation to ensure all records are included with the correct spatial reference, etc. Some data requires digitising, such as stops made in different ports by a certain vessel for example. The data is then shared as one or more feature layers, to ArcGIS Online. Feature layers act as a base for creating web maps and web scenes that are then included in AGOL apps: Dashboards, ExB and SM. These three apps usually interlink together. For example, sometimes some ExB apps are included in SMs, Dashboards apps included in ExB and so on (Figure 1).

These applications are designed to help users explore and understand the temporal aspects of historical marine data, as well as the patterns, trends and insights behind historical events. Timelines and other visualization techniques are utilized to present the data. Examples of different ways of visualizing data are shown below.

Timelines

Vessel voyages are included in the vessel records in the NMHR or can be documented in books and research reports. This kind of data is in the form of coordinates and place names (see Figure 2). Timelines can be a good visual interpretation of these voyages as they can transform dry raw data into engaging narratives that show the user the rich history beyond numbers. Timelines give the user the opportunity to visualise the vessel's journey, itinerary, historical context, and significant events.

1861 Journey Portsmouth (50.797356, -1.110298) – Stokes Bay (50.778669, -1.162579) – Cobh (then called Queenstown, Ireland 51.847497, -8.2932) – Plymouth (50.356338, -4.148671) – Portsmouth (50.797356, -1.110298) – Gibraltar (36.135914, -5.36525) – Portland (50.580783, -2.439479)

Figure 2: First sea trials of the HMS *Warrior* as stored in voyages records

Figure 4: A screenshot from the *UC70* timeline

1652 - 1654

During the First Anglo-Dutch War, Parliament ordered the building of ten new Second Rate ships, of which only three (including the *London*) were eventually completed.

3 July 1654

Admiralty Committee ordered, by Council of State, to build four second rate ships.

Captain John Taylor, Master Shipwright, Chatham submitted a 'platt' or draft for a ship:
 keel length 123' 6"
 external beam 39' 8"
 burden 1035 tons

Taylor stated that he had designed the *London* for a powerful armament, and to give '*gloree and credit for the nation*' She would be armed with the '*greatest proportion that can be borne for forraine service upon such a body.*'

Figure 5: Part of the timeline for the *London* Protected Wreck

Temporal Data - German submarines lost in British waters and their victims

As the data contained within the NMHR is so rich and varied, it was decided that a specific sub-set of data would be the subject of visualisation experimentation. Given the broad range of research undertaken by Historic England to mark the centenary of the First World War, including various projects commissioned in relation to the marine historic environment (see for example Firth 2014), records relating to the shipwrecks of that era are particularly well represented in the NMHR. Special focus was placed on the First World War and the analysis of ship losses over the years, the wrecks of German submarines, and the wrecks of civilian vessels of all nations lost during the course of the war. Various visualization techniques were used to illustrate the extent of the damage they caused to British navigation.

The map in Figure 6 shows an overview of the spatial distribution of German submarines and their victims lost in English waters. The geographical scope of submarine warfare in the area can be seen when both the submarines and the vessels they targeted are shown on the map. The visualisation also shows the overall intensity of the attacks on English coasts.

Figure 6: Map of German submarine locations and their victims.

Another example of visual representations is illustrated in Figure 7 where a 3D chart was created representing each submarine as a vertical bar. The height of each bar corresponds to the number of victims claimed by that specific submarine. This visual representation gives the user the ability to quickly compare the relative success of different submarines, highlighting those that posed the greatest threat to British shipping.

Figure 7: Locational 3D chart of German submarine victim count

The collective mapping app shown in Figure 8 focuses on the submarines with the highest count of victims. It pinpoints the locations where these submarines were lost in addition to the locations where they targeted other vessels and succeeded. This provides a spatial context for submarines operational areas and their potential. This visual representation helps to spot areas that were of high risk for shipping.

Figure 8: A collective map illustrating the subs with the highest number of victims

These examples of visual representations offer new approaches to understanding the impact of German submarines on British navigation during the First World War.

Sometimes when the data is locationally dense, it becomes hard to distinguish and comprehend. Heatmaps are then a powerful visual representation to consider. More than 1,800 vessels were lost in English waters during the First World War, so a heat map was produced to gain a deeper understanding of the spatial patterns and find out which areas of the English coast suffered the most significant losses. Locations with a higher concentration of shipwrecks are shown with a more intense heat (a brighter colour), allowing viewers to instantly identify the most heavily affected regions. The heatmap helps the user visually cluster shipwreck losses, and therefore spotting areas that experienced hazardous conditions during the First World War. The heat map illustrates very clearly the incredibly high impact of the German U-Boat campaign on shipping along the east coast of England. The transport of coal and other material from the north of England to London was crucial to the war effort. Despite efforts to ensure channels swept of mines, the instigation of sailing in convoy, and regular patrolling by warships, the toll on British merchant shipping was incredibly high.

Heatmaps can be more effective when combined with other visualisation techniques. The shipwreck heatmap in Figure 9 provides a snapshot of overall density, but taking into account changes in density over time reveals patterns in the data: areas that were likely targeted more frequently are revealed (Figure 10).

Figure 9: Heat map showing most affected areas of the British coast during the First World War

Figure 10: A sequence of maps illustrating areas of British coasts affected over the different periods of the First World War

Figure 11 presents a dynamic visualisation of war vessel losses in relation to the East Coast War Channels. When viewing these two datasets in one map, insights into the spatial distribution of shipwrecks within the context of crucial maritime routes is highlighted. By looking into the spatial relations between shipwrecks and these vital shipping lanes, we can gain a deeper appreciation for the challenges faced by mariners during the First World War. The mapping emphasises that despite the relative safety offered by the swept war channels, the sea around England was still incredibly dangerous, and merchant shipping was at a continual risk of interception and sinking by U-boats.

Figure 11: Locations of naval vessels lost in English waters in relation to East Coast War Channels

Dashboards and Statistics

Dashboards can be used to effectively consolidate spatial and temporal data, making it accessible and easily interpretable. Figure 12 showcases a dashboard application that combines a map showing the locations of First World War shipwrecks along with a graph illustrating the number of vessels lost throughout the war period in one screen. This combined view allows users to not only see where shipwrecks occurred but also to understand how the rate of sinkings changed over time.

During the First World War Germany undertook a highly effective campaign, with U-boats targeting merchant shipping around the coast of the UK. Initially the submarines would rise to the surface and give crews an opportunity to escape before the cargo vessels were sunk. However, in February 1915 a change in tactics occurred and U-boats began to sink merchant vessels without providing any prior warning. The change in tactics is identifiable in the increased volume of losses identifiable in the peak for February 1915 in Figure 12. This approach to sinking merchant vessels was halted after September 1915, partly as a result of the international condemnation that followed the sinking of the liner *Lusitania* in May 1915 off the coast of Ireland, by the German submarine *U-20*. However, this unrestricted submarine warfare was restarted later in the war during February 1917, and the increased losses among merchant shipping can be clearly seen in the dashboard.

Figure 12: First World War Shipwreck Losses over Time

Another dashboard application is shown in Figure 13 where the data is displayed in the map categorised by nationality with a corresponding bar chart. Overall, dashboards play a critical role in transforming raw maritime data into clear and interpretable narratives, enabling users to explore historical trends and draw meaningful conclusions.

Figure 13: First World War Shipwreck Distribution by Nationality

Trialling a Virtual Museum

The team also took the opportunity to explore development of a virtual museum which could be used to showcase the storymaps and data visualisation tools described above. The virtual museum piloted a public engagement tool which allows for Historic England’s marine records to be shared and experienced by users in a playful and fun environment, something quite new for a non-museum government agency. Showcasing the interactive mapping as art gallery exhibits encourages the user to explore in detail, as opposed to quickly scrolling by, as might have been the case when faced with a map on a webpage. The virtual museum can be hosted on a VR headset and forms an incredibly useful public engagement tool for showcasing marine records in an easily accessible manner.

Each wall of the Virtual Museum resembles a section of the web mapping applications. The gallery of photos link to their corresponding apps, virtual experiences or relevant links. The initial prototype version of the virtual museum was developed using BabylonJs¹¹. The user is able to move around the virtual environment and explore the content freely using a web browser only. There is no requirement for specialist plug-in software.

The 3D model used in virtual museum is a commercial product acquired through an online platform in a glTF format¹². The model was then adjusted using Blender, a free and open-source 3D creation software. The Virtual Museum was developed for the web using JavaScript¹³ and three.js library¹⁴[14] and comprises of a main hall and another hall for the First World War maps which is accessible through the main hall.

¹¹ <https://www.babylonjs.com/>

¹² glTF: a standard format for three-dimensional scenes and models

¹³ JavaScript: a programming language for the web

¹⁴ Three.js: a JavaScript library for the creation and animation of 3D content in a web browser

For every item in the Virtual Museum gallery, an info box can be opened for a brief text about that item. When clicked, each item photo opens its relevant link: a StoryMap, a virtual experience, listing entry on the National Heritage List for England, and so on. These links open as an overlay over the current page, or as new tabs depending on the content.

The main hall can be viewed in virtual reality (VR) mode, which gives the user a more immersive and engaging experience. Although the website (see Figure 14) is not currently accessible, future efforts will focus on enhancing accessibility to ensure that all users, regardless of their abilities, can seamlessly interact with and benefit from the content.

Figure 14: Trialled homepage of the virtual museum

1.3 Enhancing the NMHR – approaches to recording a spatial depiction for shipwrecks whose precise location is unknown

A major issue faced during redevelopment of the NMHR was how to create a spatial depiction for shipwreck sites whose actual location on the seabed is unknown. There are over 1,200 of these ‘Named Locations’ stored within the NMHR. Traditionally these have been ascribed to an arbitrary set of coordinates based around the position described in the loss accounts. These include relatively precise features such as rocks and reefs (for example Gull Rock, off Lundy Island, north Devon), larger sea areas which are harder to define such as mobile sandbanks (the Goodwin Sands, off Kent) and also extensive and vaguely defined areas such as “Off Beachy Head”. This method was developed prior to the inclusion of a GIS component to the data, and so the positions used were often simplified for ease of repeated typing into the system and allowed for basic spatial searches to be undertaken.

With the adoption of a GIS system, these records of documented losses were given a spatial depiction consisting of a polygon with a radius of 500m. This emphasised the imprecise nature of these positions, showing that they were only an approximation, while allowing for improved spatial searches to be

undertaken. This worked very well for well for wrecks lost off a particular seabed feature such as a rock/reef, as although the exact location is unknown, the area of seabed in which it is likely to be located is fairly limited. However for the losses with vaguer descriptions of their place of loss, this is less useful. Figure 15 illustrates the problem showing the current spatial depiction for “Off Beachy Head”. This limited depiction doesn’t maximise on the capacity of GIS Software for undertaking spatial searches, and also oversimplifies the information contained within the original documentary sources. Under the current system a wreck lost “X miles SW of Beachy Head” and another lost “Y miles SE of Beachy Head” would both get assigned to the same spatial position. While there was a benefit at the time to recording in this manner, the developments in technology allow for an improvement in recording practice. This is important as it will help to ensure that the full archaeological potential of the seabed can be considered during desk-based research in advance of offshore development.

Figure 15: The current spatial depiction of wreck “Off Beachy Head, East Sussex”

The Arches platform used for Mariner contains a data model which allows for the recording of Places. These can be either specific locations, or vaguer descriptions, making this an ideal way to describe these imprecise marine locations. The Marine Environment Data and Information Network (MEDIN)¹⁵ gazetteers for ‘sea

¹⁵ <https://medin.org.uk/>

areas', 'sea features' and 'coastline features'¹⁶ were identified as a suitable starting point for creating an accurate spatial depiction for the NMHR's named location vocabulary. It was then possible to explore multiple ways to link the named locations within Historic England's records with the pre-existing MEDIN gazetteer. Several different methodologies were trialled, involving various degrees of automation and human interpretation.

The aim of this trial was to convert named location points into polygons, which will integrate with the seabed features identified in the MEDIN Marine Gazetteers. A pilot study area was chosen, comprising an area of approximately 8,000km² located off the Norfolk coast. This area was chosen as it comprised numerous named locations, based on a mix of approximate locations, identifiable seabed features (such as sandbanks) and coastal places. Five methods were developed in an attempt to find the best approach to tackle this problem.

There were two principal challenges:

- All of the Named Location points are arbitrary which means they don't necessarily indicate an exact location of where a wreck is.
- Some of the Named Location points shared names with seabed features such as sand banks, but the positions assigned to them fell outside of the corresponding sand banks polygons as defined in the Marine Gazetteers.

Five different approaches were tested.

Approach 1: Tessellation Polygons

Methodology

A check was conducted that the Named Location points that fall inside seabed features are excluded from the point conversion analysis (the Marine Gazetteer polygons will be included as their representing polygons). A near analysis is performed to determine those points and thus removing them to a different layer. Named Location points that fell just outside Gazetteer polygons – and share the same name – are moved to be within its corresponding Gazetteer feature boundaries. This process is undertaken manually by the GIS Developer.

A spatial join was performed between the Gazetteer polygons and the Named Location points that fall within them. Using tessellation analysis, polygons were generated for the Named Location points with a predetermined shape and square area for the resulting polygons. Only polygons that contain Named Location points were chosen for further analysis. An erase function was performed using the County Boundaries to remove areas of land from the resulting polygon layer. The same is performed using the Gazetteer layer. The resulting layer from the previous step is appended with the Gazetteer layer and the result will be the new Named Location polygon layer (see Figure 16).

¹⁶ https://portal.medin.org.uk/portal/start.php?details&tpc=010_0cd97ef56ca933ce4e1c48b4f5d374fc;
https://portal.medin.org.uk/portal/start.php?details&tpc=010_3940e3af8c1c3dba5807a23d7899b547;
https://portal.medin.org.uk/portal/start.php?details&tpc=010_e2a9309c06bddcb7ff15863b40798bc9

Figure 16: A conceptual model for Approach 1 created using ArcGIS Pro Model Builder

Challenges created by Approach 1

A Gazetteer polygon may contain more than one Named Location point. When performing a spatial join, a one-to-many relationship is established, and this results in more than one overlapping polygon depending on the number of Named Location points contained within a feature from the Gazetteer polygon layer.

Gazetteer polygons could sometimes be very large and this approach doesn't provide a way to divide the polygon according to the number of Named Location points within them.

Determining the size of the tessellation polygons could be tricky as making it too large could result in more than one Named Location points within one polygon. Conversely making it too small will result in large areas of seabed being not being covered by a polygon feature (see Figure 17).

The initial comparison between the two datasets identified that there would be many instances of named locations which wouldn't have a direct comparator within the MEDIN gazetteers, as they are describing approximate positions rather than specific seabed features. This was further complicated where larger scale seabed features such as sandbanks had a one-to-many relationship with named locations. The initial approach involved the tessellation of polygons in order to create a seamless coverage of the sea area. However it became clear that this approach would further complicate matters, creating unnatural hard boundaries between features that are not based on any real world geography.

Figure 17: Tessellation polygons and sand banks

Approach 2: Thiessen Polygons (variant 1)

Methodology

The first and second steps of the first approach were applied; removing Named Location points contained within gazetteer polygons and applying spatial join between the two layers. Using Thiessen analysis, polygons were generated for each Named Location point, in a process similar to interpolation but in a vector format. An erase function was performed using the County Boundaries layer to subtract areas of land from the resulting polygon layer. The same was performed using the gazetteer layer. As with the first approach, an erase function was performed using the County Boundaries layer to remove areas of land and gazetteer polygons from the resulting polygon layer. The resulting layer from the previous step was appended with the sand banks layer and the result will be the Named Locations polygons layer.

Figure 18: A conceptual model for Approach 2 created using ArcGIS Pro Model Builder

Challenges created by Approach 2

This approach poses the same challenges as the first approach in terms of the one-to-many relationship of the spatial join in addition to the gazetteer’s large undivided polygons that contain more than one Named Location point. The resulting layer contains multipart features due to the integration of the gazetteer polygons (see Figure 19).

Figure 19: Example of a multipart feature created by Approach 2.

Approach 3: Thiessen Polygons (variant 2)

Methodology

To mark the Named Location points that fall within seabed gazetteer polygons and consequently their resulting polygons, a near analysis was performed on the Named Location points and a new field was generated in the database. Using Thiessen analysis, polygons were generated for each Named Location point. Non-marine areas were subtracted from the Thiessen polygons and overlaid with the gazetteer polygons layer. The resulting layer is the output Named Location polygon layer.

Figure 21: A conceptual model for Approach 3 created using ArcGIS Pro Model Builder

Challenges created by Approach 3

Although this approach tackles the issue of large undivided gazetteer polygons in a better way, it still contains multipart features and slivers in addition to polygons that don't contain Named Location points.

Approach 4: Raster Analysis

Methodology

To avoid the multipart features, the slivers, and multiple overlapping polygons resulting from the previous approaches, raster analysis was considered. Raster interpolation allows the integration of other layers feature edges as barriers. Gazetteer polygon edges were taken into consideration into the analysis. To divide the large gazetteer polygons that contain more than one Named Location point, interpolation analysis was performed on the gazetteer layer taking the result layer from the previous step as barriers. The two layers were combined and reconverted into one vector layer.

Figure 21: A conceptual model for Approach 4 created using ArcGIS Pro Model Builder

Challenges created by Approach 4

Some gaps appear in the resulting polygon layer, but that could be addressed to some degree by reducing the cell size in the raster analysis output.

The boundaries of the gazetteer polygons after vectorisation are not identical to the original gazetteer polygons vector layer. This could also be enhanced by reducing cell size, but they will never be identical (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Raster layer and converted vector layer

Approach 5: Buffer Areas

Methodology

Similar to the previous approaches, Named Location points matching features within the gazetteer layer were removed from the analysis. Distance between each point and the nearest point to it were calculated using the near analysis tool. This is useful for calculating the buffer radius later on to avoid overlapping of buffer polygons. Varying buffers polygons were created depending on the distance between each point and the nearest (Figure 23).

Figure 23: A conceptual model for Approach 5 created using ArcGIS Pro Model Builder

Challenges created by Approach 5

A gazetteer polygon may contain more than one Named Location point. When performing a spatial join, a one-to-many relationship is established, and this results in more than one overlapping polygon depending on the number of Named Location points inside a gazetteer polygon (Figure 24).

Figure 24: Output of the Buffer analysis

Summary of GIS research into mapping Named Locations

The five approaches trialled as part of this research have demonstrated the complexity of the data and has shown there is no single process that can be used to automate the mapping of the NMHRs named location data to the MEDIN gazetteer for marine areas. The different approaches were performed to explore different ways to tackle the issue of converting Named Location points to polygons. An approach, or a mix of approaches, can be chosen for further development. A deeper look into the challenges posed will be necessary for more accurate results.

The models developed on ArcGIS Model Builder can form a base for automation to facilitate ease of application later. However, all the approaches above cannot be fully automated. Manual verification and adjustment must be made at various stages depending on the approach.

The research and testing focused on an area of sea off the Norfolk coast which contains several large-scale seabed features in the form of sandbanks which have been a hazard to shipping for centuries. Incorporation of seabed features such as these into the national record provides an important method for predicting the likelihood of archaeological remains surviving on the seabed. This work has identified the next steps which can be applied across the whole dataset to produce a suitable resource. The importance of verification by expert users was emphasised in the results of this trial.

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1.4 Conclusions and final thoughts

The data visualisation and GIS research undertaken during the Unpath'd Waters project in support of the development of the Historic England's NMHR has showcased the richness and complexity of the data already held within internal systems. It has provided clear pointers to where data could be held in a better structure to allow visualisations to be constructed with the minimum of additional data wrangling.

As a direct result of this work, new structured data fields have been created to record information on previous voyages, relationships between attackers and victims during wartime incidents, and many other areas. This has fed back directly into the development of the new shipwreck data model structure for the English marine record. It is hoped that the successes of the Unpath'd Waters project will allow for further standardisation between the various national inventories of the UK home nations.

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